

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Mori****FIRST NAME: Kenji****PROGRAM CODE: MILT****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What distinguishes academic essays from non-academic essays?**
 - Academic essays should include the authors' original ideas that anyone in the relevant academic fields has never found.
 - Academic essays should include supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources.¹**
 - Academic essays should refer to all the credible sources which have ever been published in the relevant academic fields.
 - Academic essays should never include the authors' ideas unless credible sources support them.

2. **Why is citation or quotation necessary?**
 - To highlight words or concepts, which have become basic common knowledge in a specified academic field.

¹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4* (EUCLID, 2015), 2.

- To show an acceptance of ideas, which are issued by other experts in the relevant academic fields.
 - To avoid plagiarism, which is a severe offense that can have severe consequences in all the academic fields.²**
 - To prevent the readers, who might have little knowledge of topics of the paper, from getting bored with its contents.
3. **Where is the most appropriate place for Latin abbreviations to be used in academic papers?**
- In footnotes³**
 - In reference lists
 - In texts
 - In parentheses
4. **Which statement is a correct function of paraphrasing?**
- Use another person's ideas in their own words.
 - Express another person's ideas in fewer words.
 - Introduce another person's ideas as your ideas.
 - Present another person's ideas in your own words.⁴**
5. **In *the Turabian manual*, the author elaborates on two major citation styles. Which set of citation styles are referred to in *the Turabian manual*?**

² Ibid., 12.

³ Ibid., 78.

⁴ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, (EUCLID, 2015), 75.

- Note-bibliography style and footnotes-citation style
 - Footnotes-citation style and endnotes-citation style
 - Author-data style and note-bibliography style.**⁵
 - Endnotes-citation style and author-date style
6. **In *the Turabian manual*, the author refers to three kinds of questions that researchers should ask. According to *the Turabian manual*, which type of question is widely used by researchers in the humanities?**
- Practical questions.
 - Classical questions.
 - Conceptual questions.**⁶
 - Applied questions.
7. **Which instruction is correct for *the Harvard rule of style*?**
- Use single quotation marks for the title of an article of a journal in reference list.**⁷
 - Use double quotation marks for the title of an article of a journal in reference list.
 - Use parentheses for the title of an article of a journal in reference list.
 - Use neither quotation marks nor parentheses for the title of an article of a journal in reference list.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th ed, ed. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and the University of Chicago Press editorial staff. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 16.

⁷ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4* (EUCLID, 2015), 85.

8. **What does the Oxford style aim to do?**
- Provide a guide for public and external use.
 - Provide a guide for British scholars.
 - Provide a guide for students of the Oxford University.
 - Provide a guide for staff of the Oxford University.⁸**
9. **According to *The Bluebook*, what is a central function of a legal citation?**
- Provide readers with a variety of theories or ideas regarding topics.
 - Allow readers to locate the cited source efficiently.⁹**
 - Encourage readers to use the cited source by themselves.
 - Provide readers with evidence supporting the author's ideas.
10. **Which statement is true for academic legal citation styles adopted by *The Bluebook*?**
- Citations are placed in endnotes.
 - Citations are placed in parentheses.
 - Citations are placed in texts.
 - Citations are placed in footnotes.¹⁰**

⁸ Ibid., 99.

⁹ The Columbia Law Review, the Harvard Law Review, the University of Pennsylvania Law Review, and The Yale Law Journal, eds., *The Bluebook: A Uniform System of Citation*, 19th ed. (Cambridge: The Harvard Law Review Association, 2013), 1.

¹⁰ Ibid., 53.

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